

Energy Efficient Resource Allocation for Internet of Things (IoT)

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Abstract-Device to device (D2D) communication offers communication between users via an ultra-low latency and for this reason it is expected to play an important role in the future communication networks. D2D technology makes the basis for employing Internet of Things (IoT). One of the critical challenges in D2D communication for employing IoT using 5G technology is the resource allocation because it affects quality of service (QoS) of applications. In this paper, a novel technique for resource allocation is proposed through which battery powered devices in IoT make decisions to allocate resource blocks according to battery status. Proposed algorithm has been compared to existing resource allocation algorithms i.e. Shortest Job First (SJF) and Round Robin (RR) algorithm. Simulations have been done in MATLAB to show the performance of proposed algorithm.

Keywords: D2D Communication; Internet of Things (IoT); QoS; Energy Efficiency; Resource Allocation; 5G.

I. INTRODUCTION

Device to device (D2D) communication is the basic technology for implementation of Internet of Things (IoT) [1] and a newer paradigm for cellular networks [2]. One of the main advantages of D2D communication is ultra-low latency for communication because traversal path of signal is very short. It emphasis the concept of autonomous transfer of data which can be used in various application e.g. telematics, e-health, security etc. For now, this network is based on cellular communication but focuses for evolving towards fifth generation mobile communication system (5G). 5G network is currently in experimental phases therefore there exists a lot of challenges in deploying it efficiently. Devices used in D2D communication have small batteries which are difficult to replace or recharge therefore complex computations cannot be achieved during radio resource management [3, 4]. For this reason, energy efficiency is one of the most crucial requirements in D2D communication. Energy efficiency of each device in D2D communication must be increased by a factor of 10 at least in order to increase lifetime of batteries. Deployment of 5G network meets several requirements such as reducing latency, increasing scalability and reliability as well as it provides some functionalities that enhance the energy efficiency [5].

In this paper, an energy efficient resource allocation based on controlled access threshold (CAT) scheme has been proposed. This scheme is based on device power and uses 5G communication. At initial step, consumed power of device is compared with maximum power budget which is selected from QoS metric. QoS metric is based on power requirements in IoT applications. In the next stage, proposed solution has been optimized by inserting a threshold. The rest of paper is organised as: Previous Related work has been discussed in Section 2. System model description as well as problem formulation is given in Section 3. Section 4 elaborates the proposed solution. Simulations and results has been discussed in Section 5 and Section 6 concludes the research work.

II. LITERATURE REVIEW

A lot of research has been done related to achieve energy efficiency of D2D communication during allocation of resources by using LTE network. In [6] a resource allocation algorithm has been proposed to achieve contention based access (CBA) method. CBA method was implemented for D2D communication utilizing LTE-A network. In CBA method, latency and transmission are estimated for resource allocation by assessing probabilities of events. For any particular device resource allocation in CBA is increased if latency is greater. A random access (RA) method to allocate resources is discussed in [7]. RA method used two stages for allocation of resources. In first stage, a scheme named access class barring (ACB) is used to calculate ACB factor. This ACB factor is used by user devices to compete for resource allocation. The remaining user devices compete for new ACB check in second stage. Utilizing energy via LTE-A uplink by Type I relays is studied in [8] where authors have proposed a heuristic method. Using heuristic approach for spatial reuse of allocations of spectrum, consumption of energy is reduced. Constraints related to quality of service (QoS) requirements were introduced in [9] where a minimization problem related to sum power was used to achieve energy efficiency. Later on in [10], context information from a user device was utilized for purpose of scheduling and the subsequent system was tested for 5G network. LTE-A simulator was used for priority scheduling of context information. To achieve energy efficiency in a hybrid network containing macro-cells under femtocells layers, a game theoretic model was proposed that consists of two layers. The outer layer of proposed model allows every femtocell access point (FAP) to enhance usage of data rate to its users. Proposed solution can be achieved by Nash equilibrium. Inner layer provides energy efficiency to users depending on minimum data rate.

III. Challenges in D2D Communication

In this section, some important technical aspects as well as corresponding challenges of D2D communication has been discussed.

A. Security

As data is not stored at some central location so D2D communication needs stronger privacy of data as compared to conventional network. Various common network attacks e.g. IP spoofing, impersonification of node, malware attack etc. may paralyze D2D network. Several techniques have been discussed in [12] to protect D2D networks. In [11], authors represented a model which gives insight about three problems:

- i. Whether attacking agent is internal or external
- ii. Whether attacking agent is active i.e. it does modifications to in-transit data, or attacking agent is passive i.e. it only does snooping on data.
- iii. Whether attack is on local grounds or it is extended across network.

B. Interference Management

In D2D networks, in out-band communication links in network may suffer interference from each other as well from other devices operating in similar band [13]. Therefore resource management without interference is an active optimization problem in D2D communication. Several hybrid, distributed and centralized algorithms have been proposed to reduce interference in D2D links but there a lot of research is still active [4].

C. Synchronization

Devices in D2D communication achieve frequency and time synchronization via periodic broadcasts receiving from same base station (BS). Complications appear in the following cases: (1) User equipments (UEs) belong to different BSs, (2) Some of UEs lies in network coverage and some outside and (3) All UEs do not lie in coverage of network [14]. Although some synchronization protocols proposed for MANET and WSN may be adopted for D2D communication but in particular D2D communication needs synchronization at more accurate level. To achieve synchronization in D2D communication many MAC layer schemes [15] and physical layer schemes [14] have been proposed.

D. D2D with Mobility

Most of the research done in D2D communication is related to static users while in cellular network mobility is an important figure. More analysis is needed to analyse performance in mobility situations as well as interference handling mechanisms [16]. In D2D environment, multi-hop communication also poses a lot of challenges [17].

E. Pricing

One of the most important issues in cellular networks is pricing. In [19] various models related to pricing are proposed. Operators may provide some services which include charges e.g. security in D2D communication. Some economic models related to D2D communication describe that how UEs in D2D may sell or buy data items in cluster [19]. These models also include how cellular users may sell bandwidth to UEs in D2D [21] as well as how UE pairs in D2D may auction their resources to some waiting users [20].

F. Resource Allocation

Resource allocation, for example subcarriers, is an important task in creating and maintaining direct links in D2D communication. Different schemes related to resource allocation have been proposed by adding various constraints. In [22] a simple framework of resource allocation has been proposed.

There are many challenges in D2D communication as described. But in this research paper main aim is to focus on resource allocation constraint considering energy efficiency. So an energy efficient technique to allocate resources in D2D network has been proposed and compared with other scheduling algorithms.

IV. PROPOSED MODEL

The number of available channels is denoted by C and each channel contains resource blocks denoted by $RB[m]$ where m is the total subcarriers of each block. While utilizing resource block (d) for resource allocation, power of reference signal (P_r) which is required by the node can be computed by:

$$P_r = P_n - 10 \log_{10}(d \times S_d)$$

Where P_n is power of node and S_d is the number of subcarriers within d th any block. For calculation of general signal power consuming for a node that can create base calculations, subtract path loss PL from P_r .

$$P_{n,d} = P_r - PL$$

Signal-to-Noise Ratio SNR_n for any node n can be calculated from the following expression where δ^2 is the power of Additive White Gaussian Noise (AWGN) and $h_{n,d}$ is the channel fading amplitude.

$$SNR_n = P_{n,d} \times \frac{|h_{n,d}|^2}{\delta^2}$$

If B is the effective bandwidth and $RB[m]_n$ express the resource block that is assigned to a particular node, then data rate is given by:

$$R_n = B \times RB[m]_n \times \log_2(SNR_n + 1)$$

In this way, power consumption for all users can be measured using the below equation:

$$P_c = \sum_{n=1}^N \sum_{j=1}^{RB} P_{n,j}$$

The purpose of the system is to minimize the power P_c while assigning suitable blocks to nodes. Thus, energy efficiency can be calculated in bits/ joule using the expression:

$$E_n = \frac{R_n}{P_{n,d}}$$

The specific model for 5G network is described in [11]. Path loss is indicated by RF coverage distance.

Following formula is used to estimate the path loss.

$$PL(g) = PL(g_o) + 10 \times j \log_{10}\left(\frac{g}{g_o}\right)$$

where,

$$PL(g_o) = 20 \times \log_{10}\left(\frac{4 \times \pi \times g_o}{\gamma}\right)$$

For estimating proper conservation of energy, data transfer rate should be modelled as well. As 5G network is considered in the described model, so the data transfer rate is calculated in two ways i.e. transfer rate for cellular data (DTR_C) and transfer rate for one node to another (DTR_D).

$$DTR_C = \sum_{j=1}^m \log_2 \left[\frac{1 + P_{TC} \times G}{\sum_{y=1}^n P_{TD} \times G + \theta^2} \right]$$

$$DTR_D = \sum_{y=1}^n \sum_{j=1}^m \log_2 \left[1 + \frac{P_{TD} \times G}{P_{TC} + \sum_{y=1}^n P_{TD} \times G + \theta^2} \right]$$

where, P_{TC} is power for transmission required by cellular data transfer, P_{TD} is power for transmission required for data transfer one node to another, θ is channel noise and G is the gain of channel.

V. ENERGY EFFICIENT RESOURCE ALLOCATION WITH THRESHOLD OPTIMIZATION

Main aim of the proposed solution is to allocate resources according to consumption of energy by smaller devices. Flowchart of the proposed algorithm is given in Figure 1.

Figure 1. Flowchart of Algorithm

Each device has different energy consumption level relevant to its application so QoS factor should also be considered. The proposed solution has two phases:

- Resource Allocation relevant to QoS Metric
- Resource Allocation using threshold through an optimal strategy

For energy efficient resource allocation, power rank must be calculated by the given expression using ϕ as highest power limit:

$$\Gamma = \left[1 - \left(\frac{S(\phi_p)}{\phi}\right)\right]$$

By using the value of Γ , calculation of estimated number of carriers (λ_n) is done, that should be assigned to a particular device.

$$\vartheta_n = \left\lfloor S(\phi_p) \times \frac{1}{\Gamma} \right\rfloor - PL$$

$$b = \frac{1}{2} \left\lfloor \frac{(\vartheta_n - P_{bs})}{5} \right\rfloor$$

$$\lambda_n = 10^b$$

Now threshold ω_o is calculated which is used to update the value of Γ . By selecting suitable threshold, allocating process of carriers can be enhanced particularly for smaller devices.

$$\Gamma = \omega_o \times \Gamma$$

VI. SIMULATION AND RESULTS

Simulation is done with the help of MATLAB. Results are represented for energy efficiency as well as service probability. Measurement of successful resource allocation within available bandwidth is given by throughput probability. The results are compared with some scheduling algorithms i.e. Shortest Job First (SJF) and Round Robin (RR). Table I shows the factors used in simulation. For testing purpose, multiple values of threshold are used which are related to Table I.

TABLE I
LIST OF PARAMETERS USED

Parameters	Values
Bandwidth Available	28 GHz – 30 GHz
Spacing between Carriers	0.075 MHz
Path Loss	29
Rayleigh Channel Amplitude	28.0 dB
Rayleigh Signal Power	-10.9 dB

Figure 2 represents better performance of proposed algorithm as compared to RR and SJF algorithms with threshold 6. Similarly Figure 3 describes the better throughput probability of proposed algorithm with a threshold of 6. Better energy efficiency of the proposed algorithm can be seen in Figure 4 at threshold 10 and throughput is seen in Figure 5. Moreover, when threshold is set to 10 a throughput probability is achieved which can tolerate increasing BER. Figure 6 shows better energy efficiency for the devices with high device power at threshold 15. From the results a smooth throughput probability at threshold 15 is observed in Figure 7. Figure 8 shows the comparison between results with various values of threshold. Threshold refers to maximum limit of power which was set for simulation purpose.

Figure 2. Energy Efficiency at threshold 6

Figure 3. Throughput at threshold 6

Figure 4. Energy Efficiency at threshold 10

Figure 5. Throughput at threshold 10

Figure 6. Energy Efficiency at threshold 15

Figure 7. Throughput at threshold 15

Figure 8. Comparisons of Algorithms

VII. CONCLUSION

In this research paper, issue of resource allocation in D2D communication employing IoT via 5G has been considered. Main objective of proposed research was to increase energy efficiency for resource allocation as it is a major requirement in D2D communication. Results shows that the proposed algorithm shows better performance for resource allocation considering energy efficiency as compared to RR and SJF algorithms.

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